

RISK REGISTER REVIVAL: DEVELOPING PRESERVATION PLANNING IN A TIME OF CHANGE

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Abstract - This poster illustrates the work of a recently formed digital preservation team at the National Archives of Australia to upgrade the existing internal digital format register and risk matrix that was created in 2022 as part of a broader Risk Framework. The register is a place to centrally track and assess digital formats across a large and distributed collection. The management of digital records across several systems and locations has resulted from the various requirements and pressures of a varied collection of records that have different storage and security requirements according to format, cultural sensitivity and classification. The risk framework included a central register to track and assess digital formats across the entire digital collection.

The format register was implemented in a time of great organizational change and staff disruption and while some aspects have been successful and the collection is better tracked and understood than before, the recent settling and improvement of resources has revealed some flaws in the original design. The recent stabilization and building of a digital preservation team has allowed space to evaluate the register and refine it to a format that better supports operational needs. The process of building capability in digital preservation while building and adjusting the register embodies the theme of Haerenga (journey). The process has revealed lessons about piloting new approaches for practical application and the need to build clear processes for resilience in times of change.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The National Archives Risk Framework for digital formats was created in 2022 by the Preservation section and is based on the broader agency Risk Management Guide and the ABC method of Risk Assessment developed by the International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property (ICCROM). It also draws from the risk management cycle that is part of the ISO 31000:2009 Standard for Risk Management.

It was developed in consultation with external risk frameworks including the Library of Congress (1), Cultural Property Risk Analysis Model (CPRAM (2)), The National Archives and Records Authority (NARA) (3), and using the DPC Technology Watch publications (4) to formulate an individual high-level risk assessment tool for digital content tailored to the needs of the National Archives of Australia. The inclusion of an internal matrix to assess risk was based on prioritizing the unique needs of the Australian National Archives' collection and to account for local copyright laws, cybersecurity, and prevalence of formats and varieties of digital objects. It was implemented to compliment other high level risk mitigation policies included in the National

Archives Preservation Policy, specifically yearly benchmarking using the Digital Preservation Coalition Rapid Assessment Model (DPC-RAM).

The Digital Format Register tracks and monitors risk to the whole digital collection using both internal and/or external risk assessments for digital formats. It tracks details including PRONOM ID, technology watch, format risk assessments, research and risk mitigations over time. The risk assessments were designed to be revisited periodically, and the spreadsheet provides a date column, and prompts can be built in when further action is required. The register was set up so it can be easily populated with reports from Preservica and Mediaflex the two main systems currently managing digital records.

When a format has not been included in the PRONOM register: the digital format is allocated an internal unique identifier and process to submit the format to PRONOM is initiated. Using the Digital Format Register to map risk over the whole digital collection means that preservation planning and technology watch activities can be monitored over time and focused where they are most needed.

The recent improvement in resources has allowed the team to revisit the original design and several problems were identified in the internal risk assessment matrix. The questions were too subjective, and format evaluations were taking up too much of staff time. The previous model that required staff to allocate a risk rating to each section based on a series of questions had led to a very large number of 'moderate' risk ratings, possibly driven by a bias to allocate rankings to a middle rating.

The National Archives cannot refuse records based on format and so digital preservation staff need to engage with and manage a wide variety of formats and digital record types. The National Archives of Australia's [Digital Preservation Policy | naa.gov.au](https://naa.gov.au) uses the 'performance model' as a method to tackle the challenges inherent to this variable dispersed collection by focusing on preserving the performance of a record rather than the original format or technology. The original register was designed during a major migration of the digital collection from one preservation system into a new one. This meant the original templates for

both the audit and risk register were created while the team had no access to the digital collection.

The new team have been working to adapt the design into a more objective and efficient approach. A strong motivator behind improving the register and risk matrix was the desire to streamline it into a short triage process for initial format evaluation so the team can then focus more time-consuming technical research in the areas of highest priority. The internal risk matrix has been adapted to mimic the NARA's Preservation Planning model by implementing a formular that automatically calculates a score to allocate a risk rating to remove any bias from assessments. The register has also been edited to sort formats by type so essential characteristics can feed into evaluation work.

Some of the changes already implemented create stronger links between digital formats and digital record type to enable better comparison of formats from the same record type such as email, dataset or image files to support preservation requirements. There has also been a process to refine and edit the original questions and format of the internal format evaluation process to produce a more objective and clear process. The main goal was to streamline the process to produce a useful high-level assessment without excessive time required for ongoing maintenance, The updated version also has stronger links between formats and digital record types to assist with preservation planning work. The need to link file format risk evaluations to the archives' internal requirements around essential characteristics drove the decision to map prevalence according to record type as well as format.

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Jonathan Dennis, Assistant Manager Data Integrity, Digital Preservation, National Archives of Australia. Jonathan Dennis investigates and manages technical information and metadata for digital formats in the NAA's collection. He has worked in cultural institutions for nine years with backgrounds in curatorial work, and the conservation and digital preservation of Time-based artwork and holds a Bachelor of Arts degree from the University of Sydney in Art History & Film Theory.

Janet Ma, Manager Digital Preservation, National Archives of Australia. Janet is a dedicated professional with over a decade of experience in digital preservation, archival management, and cultural heritage digitization. With a career spanning key roles at national institutions, she has made significant

